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Synthesis of Polyaniline Nanoparticles With High Surface Area for CO₂ and N₂ Sorption

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ABSTRACT

Polyaniline nanoparticles (PANI NPs) in emeraldine salt (ES) and emeraldine base (EB) forms were synthesized via oxidative polymerization, with and without HCl stabilization, to investigate how subtle synthetic modifications affect structural, morphological, and gas sorption properties. Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) analysis confirmed the expected chemical structures and demonstrated that HCl acts as a protonic dopant and a morphological modifier. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and dynamic light scattering (DLS) measurements showed that HCl stabilization results in smaller, more uniform NPs and improved dispersion, particularly in the protonated (ES) form. Nitrogen (N₂) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) sorption studies revealed that PANI EB naturally exhibits a higher surface area and porosity due to its open-chain structure. The addition of HCl has a stronger effect on PANI ES, increasing its pore volume and gas adsorption capacity by disrupting interchain interactions. Notably, CO₂ uptake increased from 24.6 ± 1.2 to 30.6 ± 2.1 cm³/g upon stabilization, and the N₂ uptake for native PANI EB was 144.4 ± 1.3 cm³/g. This work highlights the structure–function relationship between protonation state, morphology, and gas sorption behavior. By fine tuning synthesis parameters, PANI NPs with exceptional surface areas (up to 70.8 ± 2.1 m²/g) were achieved, positioning them as promising candidates for gas sorption and related environmental applications.

1 | Introduction

Polyaniline (PANI) is a polymer that has attracted considerable attention due to its unique combination of electrical, optical, and chemical properties [1–5]. The structure of PANI is based on alternating single and double bonds in the polymer backbone. This allows it to exist in variable oxidation states, as shown in Figure 1, notably as leucoemeraldine (fully reduced), emeraldine (semi-oxidized), and pernigraniline (fully oxidized) [6]. Among these states, the emeraldine salt (ES) form is of particular interest due to its high conductivity. The emeraldine base (EB) form

exhibits excellent stability and can be reversibly doped to increase its conductivity [7].

PANI can be synthesized by various methods. The most commonly used methods include chemical oxidative polymerization [8–13], electrochemical polymerization [14–16], and interfacial polymerization [17–19]. Each type of synthesis has its advantages in terms of control over morphology, particle size, and scalability [20]. For example, oxidative polymerization is widely used due to its simplicity. It can be used to create nanostructures, and by fine-tuning reaction parameters such as monomer concen-

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FIGURE 1 | Chemical structures of three different forms of polyaniline. Source: Marvin was used for drawing, Marvin 22.11.1, 2022, ChemAxon (<http://www.chemaxon.com>).

tration, oxidant, and stabilizers, their final properties can be influenced.

Over the years, PANI has found applications in many fields. These include energy storage [21–23], sensors [24–27], anti-corrosion coatings [28–31], and catalysis [32–34]. Its inherent tunable surface chemistry and porous morphology make it particularly promising for environmental applications such as water purification and gas sorption. For CO_2 and N_2 sorption, PANI's high specific surface area, easy functionalization, and stability under various environmental conditions provide a unique opportunity for the development of advanced materials [35, 36]. In particular, the ability to synthesize PANI nanoparticles (NPs) further enhances its adsorption capabilities due to the increased active surface area and pore availability.

This study focuses on the synthesis of PANI NPs by oxidative polymerization to ES and EB form, optimized for gas sorption applications. The motivation is to achieve a high specific surface area for effective CO_2 and N_2 adsorption using favorable conditions and a simple synthesis approach. This study clarifies the relationship between the structure and properties of PANI by investigating the influence of protonation state, pore structure, and HCl stabilization. Our results show that PANI NPs are a promising material in the field of gas adsorption due to their easy availability thanks to easy preparations, without unnecessary burdens on the environment, and therefore also economically advantageous.

2 | Experimental Section

2.1 | Materials

Aniline hydrochloride ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{ClN}$, 99%, Acros Organics, Belgium), ammonium peroxodisulfate (APS— $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_8$, Penta, Czech

Republic), ammonium hydroxide (NH_4OH , 50%, Alfa Aesar, Germany), hydrochloric acid (HCl, 35%, LachNer, Czech Republic), methanol (VWR Chemical, France), distilled water. The purchased chemicals were used without further purification.

2.2 | Sample Preparation

First, 0.15 M solution was prepared by dissolving aniline hydrochloride with distilled water and 0.2 M solution by dissolving APS with distilled water at room temperature (21°C). Both solutions were placed in the refrigerator to cool to 2°C . After cooling, both solutions were mixed in 1:1 (V/V) ratio and kept under constant stirring with 400 RPM for 4 h at 2°C . Subsequently, the PANI NPs were centrifuged at 6800 RPM for 5 min and washed with distilled water and methanol. Finally, PANI NPs were dried at 50°C to obtain PANI NPs in the PANI ES form. To obtain the PANI EB form, PANI ES NPs were deprotonated in 0.5 M NH_4OH for 4 h and then centrifuged at 6800 RPM for 5 min and washed with distilled water and methanol. After washing, the NPs were dried at 50°C .

NPs stabilized with HCl were prepared using the same procedure, but 0.5 M HCl solution was added to the original solutions before mixing them together. HCl was added to the original solutions at a rate of 1 mL HCl per 10 mL of the original solution.

2.3 | Characterization Techniques

2.3.1 | Dynamic Light Scattering (DLS) and Electrophoretic Light Scattering (ELS)

The hydrodynamic diameter and electrokinetic potential of the PANI NPs were determined using a Litesizer 500 (Anton Paar, Graz, Austria) using a 658 nm (40 mW) red laser at 25°C . The samples were dispersed in distilled water at concentration of 0.5 mg per mL. The hydrodynamic diameter was analyzed through the DLS with using the disposable cuvettes ($\sim 1000\ \mu\text{L}$ per sample). Each sample was measured five times. The electrokinetic potential was analyzed through ELS with using the Omega cuvettes ($\sim 750\ \mu\text{L}$ per sample). Each sample was measured five times. All data were evaluated in Kalliope software, and electrokinetic potential was calculated using the Smoluchowski approximation method.

2.3.2 | Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

The samples were dispersed in ethanol, applied to a silicon substrate, and coated with 20 nm of gold. Next, they were examined with Tescan VEGA 3 scanning electron microscope with an overvoltage of 20 kV.

2.3.3 | Fourier-Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR)

Changes in the chemical structure of individual samples of PANI NPs were analyzed. FTIR measurement was performed by Nicolet iS50 spectrometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) using diamond ATR crystal in $400\text{--}4000\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ region with $4\ \text{cm}^{-1}$

resolution. The FTIR spectra were processed using OMNIC software.

2.3.4 | X-Ray Diffraction (XRD)

XRD pattern has been measured on Panalytical X'Pert MPD diffractometer in Bragg–Brentano reflection geometry. Constant irradiated area of primary beam (CuK_α radiation) on the sample was held by means of automatic divergence slit (ADS). Scattered x-rays were collected by using position sensitive detector (PSD, X'Celerator). Diffraction patterns were measured within range of $5\text{--}110^\circ$ 2θ with step of 0.0167° in 2θ . Collected patterns were analyzed in Fullprof Suite package [37].

2.3.5 | X-Ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

The XPS spectra were taken on an Omicron Nanotechnology machine where the primary beam is monochromatized to an energy of 1486.7 eV. The spectra were measured in the constant analyzer energy (CAE) mode at a pass energy of 30 eV. Charge compensation was used in the measurements using low energy electrons (energies down to 1.8 eV). The evaluation of the spectra was performed by CasaXPS software.

2.3.6 | Specific Surface Area and Pore Volume

Nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms were measured with the Nova 3200e instrument (Quantachrome Instruments, USA) and analyzed using NovaWin software. Samples were degassed at room temperature for 24 h, and then 66-point adsorption and desorption isotherms were measured with the nitrogen at 77 K temperature. Total specific surface area was determined using a 5-point Brunauer–Emmet–Teller (BET) analysis, and pore volume was calculated by Barrett–Joyner–Halenda (BJH) model. The maximum value of adsorption was determined as a maximum at adsorption isotherm. All samples were measured three times with an experimental error of 5% and then evaluated.

2.3.7 | CO_2 Sorption

The volume of sorbed CO_2 was determined through adsorption and desorption isotherm measurements. Before analysis, the samples underwent degassing at room temperature for 24 h. Adsorption and desorption isotherms were recorded using an Autosorb iQ gas adsorption analyzer (Anton Paar, Austria), with CO_2 as the adsorbate, at 0°C , over a pressure range of 0–760 Torr. Each sample was measured three times, with an experimental error of 5%. The maximum value of adsorption was determined as a maximum at adsorption isotherm.

3 | Results and Discussion

In the following section, we will provide a comprehensive discussion of PANI NP preparation and the individual characterization techniques used in this study. The main goal of this characterization is to compare properties of PANI NPs obtained

via preparation with and without stabilization using HCl solution and to evaluate their ability to gas sorption.

The FTIR spectra (Figure 2A) of the prepared PANI ES NPs present characteristic absorption peaks typical of its partially oxidized and protonated structure. The peak at 3347 cm^{-1} belongs to N–H stretching vibrations of secondary aromatic amines. The peak at 3210 cm^{-1} corresponds to N–H⁺ stretching of protonated imine groups, confirming the presence of doped nitrogen centers [38]. Aromatic C–H stretching is observed at 3029 cm^{-1} , and another peak at 2893 cm^{-1} corresponds to aliphatic C–H stretching vibrations. These probably arise from residual oligomers or dopant-related species. Very important are the peaks at 1556 cm^{-1} and 1471 cm^{-1} assigned to C=C stretching vibrations of quinoid and benzenoid rings. The presence of both these peaks is characteristic feature of the PANI ES. Further support for the aromatic character is provided by the C–H bending mode at 1454 cm^{-1} . The peak at 1285 cm^{-1} is attributed to C–N stretching in benzenoid units, and the peak at 1235 cm^{-1} corresponds to protonated C–N⁺ bonds associated with polaronic structures. A distinct peak at 1004 cm^{-1} belongs to the polaronic transition that is connected with delocalized charge carriers formed during protonation [39, 40]. Out-of-plane aromatic C–H deformations appear at 876 and 776 cm^{-1} , consistent with tri-substituted and 1,4-disubstituted benzene rings [41]. These confirm the substitution pattern typical of linear structure of PANI. Peaks at 685 and 565 cm^{-1} are assigned to out-of-plane N–H bending and skeletal vibrations of aromatic rings [42]. These spectral properties confirm the successful synthesis of PANI NPs in their protonated (ES) form. Although the use of HCl during the preparation does not affect the key structural and chemical properties of PANI ES, as evidenced by the similarity of the spectra, specific changes confirm its additional role as a protonic dopant. The peak at 3210 cm^{-1} , assigned to N–H⁺ stretching of protonated imines, appears with increased intensity, reflecting stronger doping. Similarly, enhanced absorption at 1235 cm^{-1} (C–N⁺ stretching) and 1105 cm^{-1} (polaron band) indicates greater charge delocalization along the polymer backbone [43].

The FTIR spectrum of PANI EB NPs (Figure 2B) shows well-defined peaks corresponding to its partially oxidized, deprotonated backbone. The characteristic N–H stretching vibrations of the secondary aromatic amines are observed at 3374 and 3270 cm^{-1} , confirming the presence of benzenoid segments [44]. Aromatic C–H stretching is evident at 3044 and 3028 cm^{-1} . The weak aliphatic C–H peaks at 2966 and 2926 cm^{-1} may originate from terminal groups or minority oxidation by-products. The core structure of PANI EB is reflected in the C=C peaks at 1585 cm^{-1} (quinoid units) and 1493 cm^{-1} (benzenoid units), confirming the emerald oxidation state. The peak at 1379 cm^{-1} is assigned to C–N stretching in the benzenoid units, whereas 1298 cm^{-1} corresponds to C–N vibrations in the secondary aromatic amines. The other peaks at 1237 and 1218 cm^{-1} are assigned to unprotonated C–N vibrations in the quinoid segments. Importantly, no intense peak is observed near 1235 or 1140 cm^{-1} , supporting the absence of protonated nitrogen forms or polaronic structures that are typical of the ES form [45, 46]. The in-plane bending of C–H appears at 1163 cm^{-1} [47], and the region around 1009 and 955 cm^{-1} shows deformation modes of aromatic rings and C–H. The out-of-plane bending peak of C–H at 823 cm^{-1} confirms the configuration of a 1,4-disubstituted benzene ring, which is

FIGURE 2 | FTIR spectra obtained on PANI ES (A) and PANI EB (B) with and without HCl stabilization. EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

consistent with the linear structure of PANI. Peaks at lower frequencies at 745, 696, 640, 602, and 586 cm^{-1} are associated with skeletal vibrations and deformation modes of the conjugate backbone [48]. These spectral features confirm the formation of PANI in its EB form, characterized by the alternation of benzenoid and quinoid units, the absence of protonation, and the absence of delocalized polarons. This is a clear difference from the conducting structure of the ES form of PANI. The spectrum of the PANI EB sample synthesized via the HCl-assisted route, followed by de-doping, shows identical peak positions to the prepared PANI EB without HCl, confirming that both materials share the same oxidation state and chemical structure. However, slightly higher peak intensities are observed in the fingerprint region (1300–800 cm^{-1}), particularly in C–N stretching and ring deformation modes. These differences are not attributed to residual protonation but rather to morphological effects introduced during synthesis. The presence of HCl is known to influence the nucleation and growth of PANI NPs, leading to more uniform and compact morphologies, which, in turn, can affect chain packing and segment orientation. Such structural differences may enhance vibrational transition dipole moments and increase absorbance in specific vibrational modes [49].

Powder XRD patterns for PANI ES and PANI ES HCl are shown in Figure 3A. Several broad peaks are clearly visible, indicating a partially ordered structure. According to the work of Pouget et al. [50], diffraction peaks of doped PANI ES can be indexed within a pseudo-orthorhombic unit cell in well-ordered samples. However, in our case, the observed broad diffraction features suggest a partially crystalline form of ES rather than a highly crystalline or metallic-like phase.

Powder XRD patterns for PANI EB and PANI EB HCl are shown in Figure 3B. The patterns display broad and low intensity features with no distinct sharp reflections, indicating that both samples are predominantly amorphous. This observation is consistent with the structural characteristics of EB form of PANI, as described by Pouget et al. [50]. According to their work, the EB form typically exists in disordered, non-crystalline form, in contrast to the more ordered doped phases (ES), which can

exhibit higher degrees of crystallinity under suitable conditions. The absence of pronounced diffraction peaks suggests that no significant long-range structural ordering is present in these samples. Therefore, PANI EB and PANI EB HCl can be assigned to the insulating EB phase with predominantly amorphous character.

To verify the different chemical states of nitrogen in the prepared PANI samples in the ES and EB forms, XPS analysis was performed in the N 1s region (Figure 4). The samples in the ES form have two main components: a signal around 399.3–399.7 eV corresponding to unprotonated benzenoid amines ($-\text{NH}-$) and a second signal around 401.0–401.3 eV assigned to protonated imine ($-\text{N}^+=$) or polaron nitrogen formed during acid doping [51, 52].

The EB samples show a dominant signal in the region of lower binding energies (398.0–398.8 eV), which is characteristic of unprotonated imine groups ($-\text{N}=\text{}$) and amine nitrogen ($-\text{NH}-$) [51, 52]. In addition, a third signal between 400.4 and 401.1 eV is visible in the EB spectra, which can be interpreted as the presence of slightly protonated or interacting nitrogen. This component corresponds to the residual presence of radical nitrogen, which is typical, for example, for partially oxidized states [51]. The presence of three components in the N 1s region of the EB form is common and reflects a complex balance between benzenoid and quinoid segments [52].

Figure 5 shows the structures of pure PANI ES and PANI EB and the structures with HCl stabilization obtained by SEM. The images show small NPs clustering into larger structures. Using ImageJ, it was found that the NPs have an average size of 177 ± 19 and 144 ± 10 nm in the case of PANI ES without and with stabilization, respectively. In the case of PANI EB, the average size of NPs without stabilization is 198 ± 37 nm and with stabilization is 142 ± 17 nm. Using HCl stabilization, it is possible to create smaller NPs and increase the homogeneity of the size distribution. It can be seen that after evaporation of the solvent used to prepare the samples for SEM, the NPs cluster into structures that are two and more micrometers in size.

FIGURE 3 | Comparisons of diffractograms of (A) PANI ES and PANI ES HCl and (B) PANI EB and PANI EB HCl. EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

FIGURE 4 | Comparison of N 1s region from XPS analysis for all PANI samples. EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

FIGURE 5 | SEM images, comparison of the structures of PANI ES (A and B) and PANI EB (C and D) in native (A and C) and stabilized (B and D) forms. SEM scanning electron microscopy.

The behavior of the synthesized PANI NPs in aqueous media reflects their chemical structure and degree of protonation. In deionized water at pH 5.5, the PANI ES is partially protonated, carrying positive charges along the polymer backbone. As expected, this results in a slightly positive electrokinetic potential (PANI ES = $+8.1 \pm 0.2$ mV), indicating limited electrostatic stabilization. When HCl was introduced during synthesis, the electrokinetic potential increased slightly (PANI ES HCl = $+8.9 \pm 0.2$ mV), likely due to more effective protonation and a more homogeneous surface chemistry. This has corresponded with a notable decrease in hydrodynamic diameter, from 3919 ± 547 to 1897 ± 241 nm, suggesting that HCl stabilization helps suppress a particle aggregation. DLS data revealed bimodal size distributions in both ES samples, which aligns with SEM observations showing that primary NPs (~ 177 nm for the unstabilized and ~ 144 nm for the HCl stabilized forms) tend to cluster into larger aggregates upon drying.

In contrast, PANI EB, which is the deprotonated and electrically neutral form of PANI, behaves differently in suspension. The measured electrokinetic potentials were negative (-6.0 ± 0.9 mV

for PANI EB, resp., -10.3 ± 0.7 mV for PANI EB HCl), reflecting the loss of protonation and reduced surface adhesion. This result for PANI EB is expected because its structure, as determined from FTIR analysis, suggests it should possess more deprotonated nitrogen groups, typically associated with a negative charge. These more negative electrokinetic potential values suggest a slight improvement in colloidal stability compared to the ES form. Hydrodynamic diameter sizes followed the same trend: PANI EB had a smaller diameter than PANI ES (2670 ± 241 nm), and HCl stabilization further reduced this value to 1804 ± 149 nm. Unlike the ES forms, both EB samples showed unimodal distributions, with DLS peaks centered around ~ 1500 nm for PANI EB and ~ 1000 nm for PANI EB HCl, indicating a more uniform dispersion and less aggregation.

Overall, the results are consistent with that would be expected based on the chemical nature of PANI in water. The protonated ES form tends to aggregate more easily due to weaker repulsive forces and stronger interparticle interactions, such as π - π stacking. Meanwhile, the EB form, especially when stabilized with HCl, shows better dispersion behavior, thanks to increased

FIGURE 6 | Comparison of N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms of PANI ES (A) and PANI EB (C) with and without stabilization with HCl (B and D). EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

electrostatic repulsion and reduced particle stickiness. This interpretation is supported by both DLS/ELS data and SEM images, which clearly show differences in particle size, distribution, and clustering across the various samples.

The N₂ adsorption and desorption isotherms (Figure 6) indicate the surface area, pore volume, and porosity differences between PANI ES and PANI EB forms, as well as the effect of HCl stabilization. These findings are further supported by FTIR analysis, which explains the materials' chemical structure and protonation state.

The nitrogen adsorption and desorption isotherms (shown in Figure 6) of all PANI NP samples showed a shape corresponding to the type IV isotherm according to the IUPAC classification. This is characteristic of mesoporous materials, indicating the presence of mesoporous capillary condensation occurring at intermediate relative pressures. The observed isotherms showed

a gradual increase in the adsorbed volume, further supporting the mesoporous nature of the materials.

In all cases, a hysteresis loop of the H3 type was observed, which is usually associated with non-rigid aggregates of plate-like particles or slit-like pores. These H3 loops are characterized by the absence of limiting adsorption at high relative pressures and are typically found in materials that do not have well-defined cylindrical or ink-like pores. The presence of this hysteresis loop is in good agreement with the morphological features detected by SEM, suggesting that PANI NPs form aggregates with interparticle voids.

As it is clear, the specific surface area and pore volume measurements show differences between PANI ES and PANI EB, both in their natural and HCl stabilized states (Table 1). Adding HCl to stabilize these materials doesn't just tweak their chemistry, and it also affects how well they absorb gases like nitrogen. For

TABLE 1 | Comparison of the maximum absorbed gas (N₂ or CO₂) volumes on polyaniline (PANI) emeraldine salt (ES) and PANI emeraldine base (EB) with and without stabilization with HCl.

Sample	Pore volume (cm ³ /g)	Max. N ₂ sorbed volume (cm ³ /g)	Max. CO ₂ sorbed volume (cm ³ /g)
PANI ES	0.132 ± 0.006	94.1 ± 3.4	24.6 ± 1.2
PANI ES + HCl	0.209 ± 0.004	107.9 ± 1.4	30.6 ± 2.1
PANI EB	0.152 ± 0.004	144.4 ± 1.3	29.7 ± 2.4
PANI EB + HCl	0.195 ± 0.013	138.4 ± 2.2	27.8 ± 2.3

FIGURE 7 | Comparison of pore size distribution for (A) PANI ES and (B) PANI EB with and without stabilization with HCl. EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

PANI ES, HCl stabilization noticeably improves its performance. The maximum amount of nitrogen it can absorb increases from 94.1 ± 3.4 to 107.9 ± 1.4 cm³/g, which correlates well with a boost in pore volume and surface area. This happens because HCl causes the material to swell slightly and disrupts some of the tight connections between polymer chains, which creates more space for gas to enter. FTIR analysis confirms that even after stabilization, PANI ES stays in its protonated form, and the typical spectral bands linked to protonated nitrogen are still there. So, although the chemical structure remains protonated, the HCl treatment still brings structural changes that open up the material and make it more porous.

PANI EB form is a slightly different. Here, HCl has only a minor effect. Nitrogen uptake after stabilization decreases from 144.4 ± 1.3 to 138.4 ± 2.2 cm³/g, indicating that the porous structure of PANI EB does not benefit significantly from the addition of HCl. The FTIR data further support this, as the deprotonated imine groups remain unaltered, ensuring the structure's stability and rigidity. In short, HCl has a significantly stronger effect on PANI ES, helping to open up its structure and increase its sorption capacity. The impact on PANI EB, which already has a more open and stable setup, is minimal.

The pore size distribution profiles (Figure 7) confirm the structural variations among PANI (ES or EB) samples and highlight the unique impacts of HCl stabilization. PANI ES in its native form has a narrower distribution and a substantially reduced

pore volume, indicating a more compact structure due to electrostatic interactions between protonated nitrogen species. HCl stabilization of PANI ES has a significant effect on increasing the pore volume and expanding the distribution to wider pore widths. In contrast, PANI EB in its native form has a higher pore volume, confirming its naturally open and porous structure, which is consistent with its high nitrogen sorption capacity. After HCl treatment, PANI EB HCl retains a similar distribution profile with only a slight decrease in total pore volume.

Adsorption and desorption isotherms were used to determine the specific surface area of PANI ES and PANI EB samples, both native and stabilized. Table 2 compares specific surface area values for PANI structures to those published in previous works. In this study, particles with the highest specific surface area were synthesized using simple oxidative polymerization, and the increase in surface area was up to seven times more than in previous studies. Only one study reported a higher value, although the microspheres were prepared at high temperatures in an autoclave [53]. Except for this one work, particles with the highest specific surface area, in comparison with previous authors, were prepared now in this study in all cases of PANI ES and PANI EB.

The CO₂ sorption efficiency of PANI materials indicates how their chemical structure affects their gas sorption ability (Table 1). PANI ES has the CO₂ adsorption capacity of 24.6 ± 1.2 cm³/g, which increased to 30.6 ± 2.1 cm³/g after stabilization with

TABLE 2 | Comparison of our surface-specific area results with previously published ones.

Sample	Type of synthesis	Morphology	Surface area (m ² /g)	Refs.
PANI	Oxidative polymerization	Intertwined fibers	22.8	[8]
PANI	Oxidative polymerization	Nanofibers	9.1	[9]
PANI ES	Interfacial polymerization	Nanofibers	48.8	[17]
PANI	Oxidative polymerization	Granular samples	26.3	[10]
PANI ES	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	42.1	[11]
PANI ES	Oxidative polymerization	Agglomerates	15	[12]
PANI	Oxidative polymerization	Granular	11	[12]
PANI EB	Oxidative polymerization	Coral-like grains	29	[12]
PANI	250°C in an autoclave	Microspheres	80.5	[53]
PANI	250°C in an autoclave	Macrospheres	46.3	[53]
PANI	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	18.4	[13]
PANI	High-pressure autoclave	Nanorods	26.6	[13]
PANI ES	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	50.2 ± 2.4	This work
PANI ES + HCl	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	56.5 ± 1.5	This work
PANI EB	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	65.3 ± 0.9	This work
PANI EB + HCl	Oxidative polymerization	Nanoparticles	70.8 ± 2.1	This work

Abbreviations: EB, emeraldine base; ES, emeraldine salt; PANI, polyaniline.

HCl. This increase can be most likely caused by the breaking of some of the compact structure in PANI ES, as HCl introduces protonated nitrogen species that interact more strongly with CO₂ molecules. The protonated sites in PANI ES + HCl, as indicated by FTIR, can generate electrostatic interactions with CO₂, increasing the material's adsorption efficiency. PANI EB's deprotonated, open-chain structure results in a greater CO₂ sorption capacity (29.7 ± 2.4 cm³/g). This configuration improves the accessibility of CO₂ molecules to adsorption sites. When stabilized with HCl, PANI EB's capacity decreases slightly to 27.8 ± 2.3 cm³/g. The decreased activity could be due to a minor restructuring of the polymer chains caused by HCl. It could limit the availability of certain adsorption sites without materially affecting the overall structure. The pore volume information helps to clarify these disparities. The pore volume of native PANI ES is 0.132 ± 0.006 cm³/g; however, it increases significantly to 0.209 ± 0.004 cm³/g after HCl stabilization (presented in Table 1). This is consistent with its improved CO₂ sorption. PANI EB has a greater native pore capacity (0.152 ± 0.004 cm³/g), which increases to 0.195 ± 0.013 cm³/g after stabilization. However, for PANI EB, this increase in pore volume is not reflected into increased sorption capacity, suggesting that pore accessibility and chemical affinity of adsorption sites are equally relevant.

According to FTIR research, the protonated nitrogen species in PANI ES and PANI ES + HCl are important for their CO₂ sorption capacity because they generate favorable interactions with CO₂ molecules. Meanwhile, the deprotonated imine and quinoid structures in PANI EB and its stabilized form provide stable but less specific interaction contexts for CO₂ [54]. These differences explain why PANI EB keeps a high sorption capacity, but HCl stabilization does not increase performance. Together, these findings highlight the structure–function connection in CO₂

sorption. PANI ES benefits from stabilization, which improves pore structure and CO₂ interactions, whereas PANI EB takes advantage of its naturally open and accessible structure.

4 | Conclusions

We have successfully synthesized PANI NPs in both of PANI ES and PANI EB forms. We have thoroughly investigated how the presence or absence of HCl during synthesis affects their structure, morphology, dispersion, and gas sorption properties. Our results showed that HCl plays a key role not only in stabilizing the NPs but also in subtly tuning their chemical structure and behavior in aqueous environments. FTIR analysis confirmed the expected chemical structures for both forms, with clear signs of protonation in PANI ES and deprotonation in PANI EB. Importantly, using HCl during synthesis did not alter the core chemical structure but did enhance doping levels in PANI ES, which correlated with increased charge delocalization. XRD analysis confirmed that PANI in the protonated ES form is partially crystalline, whereas PANI in the deprotonated EB form has a predominantly amorphous character. SEM and DLS analyses revealed that HCl stabilization leads to smaller, more uniform NPs and better dispersion in water, especially in the ES form, which otherwise tends to aggregate due to its positive surface charge and strong interparticle interactions. In contrast, PANI EB, being deprotonated and more neutral, showed better natural dispersion and greater colloidal stability, further improved by HCl treatment.

Finally, gas sorption experiments highlighted significant differences in surface area and porosity, and consequently in sorption capacities, between the ES and EB forms. PANI EB consistently

exhibited higher gas uptake capacity ($144.4 \pm 1.3 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g N}_2$), thanks to its more open structure and increased pore accessibility. By optimizing the synthesis conditions, we were able to prepare NPs with the highest specific surface area compared to other oxidative polymerization approaches and other authors ($70.8 \pm 2.1 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for PANI EB HCl). HCl treatment noticeably improved the performance of PANI ES by promoting pore formation and increasing both surface area and gas adsorption, particularly for CO_2 ($30.6 \pm 2.1 \text{ cm}^3/\text{g}$). This study shows how a minor modification of synthesis, like the addition of HCl, can influence not only the physical properties of PANI NPs but also their efficiency in applications such as gas sorption. These findings add to the expanding promise of PANI-based materials in environmental or energy related applications that require higher specific surface area and dispersibility control.

Author Contributions

Jaroslava Jarolímková: conceptualization, methodology, validation, investigation, writing – original draft, visualization, writing – review and editing. **Viktorie Neubertová:** investigation, writing – original draft. **Filip Mamoň:** investigation. **Stanislav Daniš:** investigation. **Petr Sajdl:** investigation. **Zdeňka Kolská:** validation, supervision, funding acquisition.

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Ethical Statement

The authors have nothing to report.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15266846>.

Peer Review

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